

Fluorescent Reagents: Part II

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2,5-Dimethoxy benzhydrazide; 3-Nitro, 2,5-dimethoxy benzhydrazide; 2,5-dimethoxy benzoyl chloride and 3-nitro-2,5-dimethoxy benzoyl chloride have been synthesised and their applications in ultrachromatograms has been studied.

In continuation of our previous work¹, we report here the synthesis of four more fluorescent reagents namely, 2, 5-dimethoxy-benzhydrazide, 3-nitro-2,5-dimethoxy-benzhydrazide, 2, 5 dimethoxy-benzoyl chloride and 3-nitro-2, 5-dimethoxybenzoyl chloride. All these four compounds and their derivatives in ethanolic solution have been found to be fluorescent in U. V. light.

Hydroquinone obtained by Robinson's² method was converted into 2, 5 dimethoxybenzoic acid using Lang's³ procedure. Nitration of the preceding acid using Pianska's⁴ procedure afforded 3-nitro-2, 5-dimethoxybenzoic acid. The two acids have been converted into the corresponding hydrazides (I, X=H; X=NO₂) and acid chlorides (II, X=H; X=NO₂) by treating their methyl ester with 80% hydrazine hydrate, and acids with thionyl chloride.

EXPERIMENTAL*

Methyl 2,5-Dimethoxybenzoate—(i) 2,5— Dimethoxybenzoic acid (6 g.), methanol (100 ml.) and sulphuric acid (conc. 5 ml.) were refluxed for 12 hr. The excess of methanol was distilled and the residue extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed successively with water, sodium bicarbonate solution, again with water and dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate. The residue after the removal of ether was distilled under reduced pressure (b.p. 135°/4 mm.) to yield (4 g.) of a colourless liquid, which emits a deep blue fluorescence when exposed to UV light. (Found: C, 61.1; H, 6.2; C₁₀H₁₀O₄ requires: C, 61.2; H, 6.1%).

1. Devgan, Gupta and Bokadia, *J. Ind. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 42, 395.
2. Robinson and Smith, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 393.
3. Villani and Joseph Lang, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 2301.
4. Barany and Pianska, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 965.

*All the m.p.s. are uncorrected.

(ii) Through a solution of 2:5-dimethoxybenzoic acid (1g.) in methanol (15 ml.) dry HCl gas was passed for 1 hr. The contents were refluxed for 4 hr. and then cooled. Dry HCl gas was again passed for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. and the refluxing was continued for another 2 hr. The contents after removal of excess of methanol were extracted with ether and the ethereal extract was worked out as before to yield a colourless compound (0.6 g.) which on co-chromatography with a sample obtained by sulphuric acid method showed single spot on TLC.

2:5-Dimethoxybenzhydrazide.—Hydrazine hydrate (80%, 3 ml.) was taken in a flask and to it was added methyl 2:5-dimethoxybenzoate (3 g.) dropwise with constant shaking. The contents were refluxed on a water bath for 15 min. and then methanol (50 ml.) was added and the refluxing continued for another 2 hr. The excess of methanol was removed and the contents cooled, when white needle shaped crystals separated. They were filtered, washed with little ether and further crystallised from methanol to yield (2 g.) colourless needles, m.p. 92°. Its ethanolic solution emits blue fluorescence even in day light. (Found: C, 54.8; H, 6.3; N, 14.31; $C_9H_{10}O_5N_2$ requires: C, 55.1; H, 6.1; N, 14.29%.)

3-Nitro-2:5-dimethoxybenzoic Acid.—2:5-Dimethoxybenzoic acid (5 g.) was dissolved in the minimum quantity of glacial acetic acid and to it the nitrating mixture (15 ml.), prepared by dissolving nitric acid (4.2 ml, d 1.42) in glacial acetic acid (37.8 ml.), was added in one lot at the room temperature. The contents were shaken well and then warmed on a water bath until it became brown. It was cooled and poured on ice-cooled water. The yellow solid thus separated was kept in the freeze for over night, filtered, washed with a little ice-cooled water and recrystallised from absolute alcohol in yellow needles, m.p. 159°, (yield, 4 g.). Ethanolic solution of this nitro acid emits amber coloured fluorescence in UV light. (Found: C, 47.8; H, 4.2; N, 6.03; $C_9H_8O_6N$ requires: C, 47.6; H, 4.0; N, 6.17%.)

Methyl 3-Nitro-2:5-dimethoxybenzoate.—(i) A mixture of 3-nitro-2:5-dimethoxybenzoic acid (3.5 g.), methanol (50 ml.) and sulphuric acid (conc. 3 ml.) was refluxed for 12 hr. After distilling off the excess of methanol, the residue was poured in water (25 ml.) and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed successively with water, sodium bicarbonate solution, again with water and dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate. The residue after ether removal, was crystallised from ethanol to yield yellow plates (2.8 g.), m.p. 93°. Its ethanolic solution emits amber coloured fluorescence in UV light. (Found: C, 49.6; H, 4.6; N, 5.84; $C_9H_8O_6N$ requires: C, 49.8; H, 4.5; N, 5.81%.)

(ii) Through a solution of 3-nitro-2:5-dimethoxybenzoic acid (1 g.) in methanol (20 ml.) dry HCl gas was passed for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr, while the contents being kept cooled in the freezing mixture bath. It was then refluxed for 3 hr., cooled and again HCl gas was passed for 15 min. and refluxed again for 1 hr. The contents were worked up as before to yield yellow plates (0.5 g.), m.p. and mixed m.p. 93° with the sample obtained by conc. sulphuric acid method.

(iii) 2:5-Dimethoxybenzoate (0.5 g.) was dissolved in the minimum quantity of glacial acetic acid and to this nitrating mixture (1.5 ml) prepared by the method described before, was, added at room temperature. The contents were shaken and warmed on a water bath till the colour turned brown, cooled and poured into a beaker containing crushed ice. A yellow compound precipitated out, which was filtered and crystallised from etha-

not to yield plates (0.3 g.), (m.p. and mixed m.p. 93° with the samples prepared by either of the above two methods).

3-Nitro-2:5-dimethoxybenzhydrazide.—Hydrazine hydrate (80%, 3 ml.) was taken in a flask and to it the preceding nitroester (3 g.) was added portionwise, the contents were heated under reflux for 10 min, ethanol (10 ml.) was added and the refluxing was continued for another 2 hr. Removal of the excess of ethanol yielded needles which were recrystallised from ethanol in the form of yellow silky needles, m.p. 183°, (yield 2.1 g.). Its ethanolic solution when spotted on a filter paper emits amber coloured fluorescence. (Found: C, 45.0; H, 4.6; N, 17.43; $C_9H_{11}O_5N_3$ requires: C, 44.8; H, 4.5; N, 17.45%.)

General Procedure for the Preparation of Hydrazones of Aldehydes and Ketones.—The hydrazide (0.3 g.) was dissolved in the minimum quantity of ethanol by warming. The carbonyl compound slight less than the molecular proportion as such if liquid, otherwise its alcoholic solution along with a trace of glacial acetic acid was added to the hot solution. If necessary, the contents were heated on a water bath for 3-4 min. On cooling, the hydrazones separated and were crystallised from ethanol (No. 6 crystallised from petroleum). Melting points and analytical data of the hydrazones prepared are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

No.	Carbonyl compound	M.P.*	Colour of fluorescence	Formulae of Hydrazones	C%		H%		N%	
					Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.
1.	Citral	220 de-com.	Light blue	X=H; $C_{10}H_{16}O_2N_2$	68.90	69.09	7.91	7.88	8.99	8.48
2.	Benzaldehyde	153	Slaty	X=H; $C_{16}H_{16}O_2N_2$	—	—	—	—	9.79	9.86
3.	Salicylaldehyde	123	Blue	X=H; $C_{16}H_{16}O_4N_2$	—	—	—	—	9.20	9.33
		188	Amber	X=NO ₂ ; $C_{16}H_{14}O_6N_3$	—	—	—	—	12.05	12.17
4.	Acetophenone	196	Blue	X=H; $C_{17}H_{18}O_2N_2$	—	—	—	—	—	—
		195	—	X=NO ₂ ; $C_{17}H_{17}O_3N_3$	—	—	—	—	—	—
5.	Camphor	170	Amber	X=NO ₂ ; $C_{19}H_{23}O_3N_3$	60.05	60.08	6.71	6.67	11.07	11.2
6.	Bromo camphor	181	Light blue	X=H; $C_{19}H_{25}O_3N_3$ Br	(Found: Br	—	—	—	—	—
		202	Amber	X=NO ₂ ; $C_{19}H_{24}O_3N_3$ Br	—	—	—	—	—	—

TABLE II

No.	Name of compound	M.P.*	Colour of fluorescence	Formula of Benzozate	C%		H%	
					Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.
1.	α-Terpineol	55	Blue	X=H; $C_{19}H_{26}O_4$	71.58	71.69	8.3	8.17
		95	Purple	X=NO ₂ ; $C_{19}H_{24}O_6N$	63.01	62.81	7.01	6.89
2.	Menthol	42	Blue	X=H; $C_{19}H_{26}O_4$	71.01	71.25	8.69	8.75
3.	Aniline	86	—	X=H; $C_{13}H_{13}O_2N$	—	—	—	—
4.	p-Nitrophenol	240 de-com.	—	X=NO ₂	—	—	—	—

2:5-Dimethoxybenzoyl Chloride.—2:5 Dimethoxybenzoic acid (3 g.) was taken in a quick-fit flask provided with a double surface reflux condenser, thionyl chloride (8 g.) added and the contents heated on a water bath with occasional shaking for 2 hr. Excess

of thionyl chloride was distilled off and the residue distilled under reduced pressure, to yield (2.1 g.) a colourless liquid (b.p. 127-128°/1.5 mm.). (Found: Cl, 15.95; $C_9H_5O_3Cl$ requires: Cl, 16.40%).

3-Nitro-2:5-dimethoxybenzoyl Chloride.—3-Nitro-2:5-dimethoxybenzoic acid (3 g.) was treated with thionyl chloride (8 g.) in the same manner as given above. Excess of thionyl chloride was distilled off and the residue crystallised from dry carbon tetrachloride to yield (1.8 g.) yellow needles, m.p. 76°. (Found: Cl, 14.31; $C_9H_5O_3N$ Cl requires Cl, 14.66%).

Various benzoates described in table II were prepared by usual procedure using pyridine as a base and they were crystallised from ethanol (No. 1, $X=NO_2$ crystallised from petroleum).

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